

Relationship Between Occupational Stress and Burnout Tendencies Among Secondary School Teachers in Anambra State

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between occupational stress and burnout tendencies among secondary school teachers in Anambra state. It was guided by five research questions and seven null hypotheses. Correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. A total of 2000 teachers were sampled from the population of 5634 teachers in government owned secondary schools in the state using proportionate stratified random sampling. The instruments that were used for this study include Occupational Stress Inventory for Teachers (OSIT) and Teachers Burnout Inventory (TBI). They were validated and tested for reliability. The data relating to research questions one and two were analysed using aggregate scores, percentages. Then, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was adopted for research questions 3 to 5. Also, data relating to the hypotheses 1-3 were tested using a t-test of correlation coefficient. Hypotheses 4 and 5 were tested using a Z-test; while hypotheses 6 and 7 were tested with Analysis of variance (ANOVA). From the analysis, the following findings were made among others: Majority of the teachers experience low or moderate occupational stress. Most of the teachers have low burnout tendency. There is very low or no negative relationship of 0.06 existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of secondary school teachers in Anambra state. There is low negative relationship of -0.32 existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of male secondary school teachers in Anambra state. There is very low positive relationship of 0.19 existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of female secondary school teachers in Anambra state. There is significant very low or no negative relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of secondary school teachers in Anambra state. Based on the findings recommendations were made.

Introduction

Stress at work resulting from increasing complexities of work and its divergent demand has become a prominent and pervading feature of many occupations. School environment is frequently demanding, requiring workers to be environmentally involved with students as well

as being mentally and physically challenged. This means, according to Jones and Kagee (2005) that teachers in general are exposed to various duty-related stressors that are significantly different, in terms of quality and quantity to those experienced by the general population. For instance, teachers experience a lot of negative emotions arising from the challenges of work overload, anxiety, and anger, frustration. Some may even get to the extent of becoming depressed.

Relationship between Occupational Stress and Burnout Tendencies Among Secondary School Teachers In Anambra State teachers experience as a result of their work. Stress has effects on a person's physical, emotional and psychological well-being. Stress manifests in many ways. Stress manifestations may be physiological, psychological, and behavioural. Occupation related stress has negative consequences on both individual and the work/occupation. Teachers may experience occupational stress following some factors such as technological uncertainty, work overload, demanding and insensitive boss, family issues, personal economic problems, and of course personality characteristics. Such occupational stress may escalate to burnout causing low productivity, dissatisfaction, and the tendency to leave job in some cases.

Stress is also referred to as negative emotional experiences with associated behavioural, biochemical, and physiological changes that are related to acute or chronic challenges (Robinson, 2007; Sarason & Sarason, 2008). Earlier, Robbins (2001) defines stress as a dynamic condition in which an individual is confronted with an opportunity, constraint, or demand related to what he or she desires and for which the outcome is perceived to be both uncertain and important. Stress is often conceptualized as a process whereby environmental factors called stressors may increase the likelihood that a person will feel stressed, which is an internal state characterized by arousal and displeasure. For the purpose of this study, occupational stress is defined as a condition wherein job related factors interact with the individual to change his or her psychological or physiological conditions in such a way that the individual is forced to deviate from the normal functioning. Long term experience of stress can lead to adverse responses termed strain (Aftab & Khatoon, 2012)

Studies have reported negative organizational consequences of academic stress, including lowered productivity (Hassan, 2014; Malow-Iroff & Johnson, 2006; Jacobs, Tytherleigh, Webb, & Cooper, 2007). For instance, in the United Kingdom (U.K.), academics had low levels of organizational commitment and expressed dissatisfaction with their jobs, pay, and benefits (Tytherleigh, Webb, Cooper, & Ricketts, 2005). In addition, Australian academics were dissatisfied with their jobs; and more specifically with hours of work, industrial relations, promotion opportunities, and pay. If this applies to Anambra state school system, it becomes bad news for the management of school system because high job satisfaction contributes to better outcomes.

The Health and Safety Executive (2006) in the United Kingdom reported that teaching was the most stressful occupation. Studies carried out in Malaysia identified several factors contributing to stress among teachers, such as use of information technology, years of experience in teaching, the working environment and feelings of responsibility; the school type and

perceptions of inadequate school facilities (Chan, 2006; Hanizah, 2003). Similarly, Nigerian teachers seem to be having a hard bite of the stressful recipe because teaching in Nigeria is like experiencing a “political football” game as a result of changes in government, government frequent demands, change in policy and poor remuneration (Agbatogun, 2010). Teaching like other professions involves stress as an inevitable tool of challenges, flavour and change which adds zest for living (Agbatogun, 2010)

According to Sargent (2012) occupational stress occurs when a person is unable to fulfill the expectations and challenges in the workplace. When this happens, the person loses control over seemingly normal situations that are regularly experienced at work, which leads to poor performance, job dissatisfaction and eventually, depression. According to Mitchell, McGee, Moltzen and Oliver (2003) the pressure to keep up with the assessment requirements and paper work has been a tremendous personal cost to teachers. Along with these challenges has been an insistence that teachers demonstrate excellence in their teaching so that students produce positive learning outcomes. As Agbatogun (2010) has noted, this has fuelled unrealistic expectations about what teachers can and should accomplish. Many anecdotal reports amongst some school teachers have suggested that effect participation in school organizations has become increasingly stressful and is continuing to have profound effects on teachers’ physical health and mental well-being. In studying occupational stress, researchers have focused on three or four main approaches as ways to conceptualize stress. The first category is the stimulus-based approach derived from the engineering approach. In this approach, researchers have concentrated on stress as a phenomenon which is extraneous to the individual, with no account taken of the individual perceptions or experience (Devonport, Biscoomb, & Lane, 2008). This approach views stress as a destructive environmental agent.

The second category is the response-based or medico-physiological/psychological approach where researchers focus on stress as a response to stimuli that may be a disturbing situation on environment. The level of analysis of this approach has often been concerned with disturbances of biological systems. The third and the fourth category are interactionists or transactional approach which reflects a psychological orientation. This approach emphasizes the importance of the way individuals perceive and react to situations which are forced upon them; it reflects therefore a ‘lack of fit’ between the individual and the environment. These models have been termed ‘psychological’ because they take into account the cognitive processes and emotional reactions which underpin those interactions. The four approaches do cover common ground, mainly differ in the definition they propose and the methodology used to investigate the stress. Psychological stress, as Lazarus (1999) noted cannot be solely confined in the environment itself or just as the result of personality characteristics. He acknowledges that it is dependent on a particular kind of person-environment relationship and therefore the struggle to adapt to life may be termed stress. Other words that have been used in the past as a substitute for stress are: conflict, frustration, trauma, anomie, alienation, anxiety, depression, and emotional distress (Lazarus, 1999). He distinguished three types of psychological stress namely harm/loss, threat, and challenge. In harm/loss type of stress, it is recognised that the damage or loss has already taken place. Threat stress focuses on harm or loss that has not yet occurred but is likely to occur in the

near future. While Challenge stress sees that although difficulties may be encountered when something needs to be gained, these inform difficulties could be overcome. These three types are coped with differently and have different psycho-physiological and performance outcomes. Empirical evidences have shown that, teachers experiencing more stress have the tendency to burnout (Health Information publication, 2005; Kokkinos, 2007; Moore, 2001). The manifestation of burnout is a function of stressors engendered at both the environmental, organization and personal levels. Burnout is defined as a chronic affective response pattern to stressful work conditions that feature high levels of interpersonal contact. Maslach, Schaufeli and Leiter (2005) conceptualized burnout as consisting of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment. Emotional exhaustion refers to the feeling of being emotionally over-extended, tired and fatigued. Depersonalization refers to the tendency to develop negative, cynical, callous or detached attitudes towards the people with whom one works. The Third component is the loss of or reduced feeling of personal accomplishment derived from jobs and employees often evaluate themselves negatively (Maslach, Schaufeli & Leiter, 2005).

Burnout is described as the inability to perform both functionally and effectively in employment settings due to extensive exposure to job-related stress (Dorman, 2003). Burnout tendency means that there is likely possibility that teachers who experience stress will not perform functionally and effectively in the employment settings. Burnout is further conceptualized as referring to individuals' feelings that they have depleted or exhausted their cognitive, physical, and emotional resources (Melamed, Shirom, Toker, Berliner & Shapira, 2006). Burnout is conceived as a work-related stress syndrome, originally observed among workers in the human services (Maslach, Jackson, & Leiter, 1996). However, research such as Bakker, Demerouti and Schaufeli (2002) has shown that the two core dimensions of burnout-exhaustion, and cynicism or disengagement from work—can be observed in virtually any occupational group.

Burnout is characterized by exhaustion, cynicism, and reduced professional efficacy (Maslach, 2003). Research on burnout has been highly productive in terms of identifying burnout symptoms, antecedents, consequences, and developmental processes, as well as the effects of different interventions. It is typically seen as a syndrome of emotional exhaustion, cynicism, and reduced personal efficacy (Maslach, 1982; Maslach, Schaufeli, & Leiter, 2001). It refers to a process in which the individual's attitudes and behaviours change in negative ways in response to job stressors. It is a process of progressive disillusionment—a loss of energy, idealism, and enthusiasm (Lokanadha & Poomima, 2012; Schaufeli, Maslach, & Marek, 1993).

Gender differences have been noted in teachers experiencing occupational stress (Aftab & Khatoon, 2012; Akomolafe, 2011; and Duyilemi, 1995). With the rapid change in society the role of women is changing. Studies have shown that differences exist between male and female teachers in experiencing occupational stress (Jonas, 2001, Ngidi & Sibaya, 2002).

This study assumes that school location (rural/urban) will also play some roles in secondary school teachers' experience of occupational stress in relation to burnout. Thus, gender and location are important study variables of the present study. Generally, the negative consequences of stress and burnout are tremendous on jobs and individuals. The researcher is of

the view that teacher burnout may have a negative impact on the teachers themselves leading, for instance, to emotional and physical ill-health, and on the students. This is because teachers experiencing burnout may be relatively impaired in the quality of teaching and commitment. Again, such teachers tend to give less information and less praise as well as interact less with students. Teachers, especially those teaching in secondary schools in Anambra State work so hard to ensure that they discharge their assigned duties and deliver on their job of teaching students. Due to the usual attendant large population of students, with an average of about 50 students per class in most public secondary schools in the state, teachers have enormous and challenging task which often tell on their health and the way they handle issues. Such situation could easily lead to both physical and emotional exhaustion and may possibly affect their output.

Also, it is of note that some of these teachers, despite having an enormous workloads assigned to them in schools, engage in activities which differ significantly from their specified duties. For instance, many of these teachers engage in sales of different items, both within the school and outside the school settings to make ends meet; and whole lot of other things different from their normal duties of teaching. Situation like this is not good for the school children whom these teachers are meant to take care of.

A good number of researches investigated stress and burnout separately. Some of these studies that have been carried out on stress and burnout among teachers both within and outside the country include: Agbatogun (2010); Akomolafe (2011); Lokanadha and Poomima (2012) who looked critically at issues of stress and burnout. However, the present researchers observe that there is rareness of research on the relationship between occupational stress and burnout tendencies among secondary school teachers in Anambra state. This has engineered these researchers towards conceiving he need for this study; to investigate the relationship between occupational stress and burnout tendencies among secondary school teachers in Anambra state.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study investigated the relationship between occupational stress and burnout tendencies among secondary school teachers in Anambra state, specifically the study intends to determine;

1. The occupational stress scores of secondary school teachers in Anambra state.
2. The burnout tendencies scores of secondary school teachers.
3. The relationship between the occupational stress scores and burnout tendencies scores secondary school teachers.
4. The relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of male secondary school teachers in Anambra state?
5. The relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of female secondary school teachers in Anambra state?

Research Questions

The following research questions where formulated to guide the study:

1. What are the occupational stress scores of secondary school teachers in Anambra state?
2. What are the burnout tendencies scores of secondary school teachers in Anambra state?

3. What is the relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendencies of secondary school teachers in Anambra state?
4. What is the relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of male secondary school teachers in Anambra state?
5. What is the relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of female secondary school teachers in Anambra state?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were stated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. There is no significant relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendencies of secondary school teachers in Anambra state.
2. The relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of male secondary school teachers in Anambra state is not significant
3. The relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of female secondary school teachers in Anambra state is not significant
4. There is no significant difference in the occupational stress scores of secondary school teachers based on gender.
5. There is no significant difference in the burnout tendency scores of secondary school teachers based on gender.
6. There is no significant difference in the occupational stress scores of secondary school teachers based on location.
7. There is no significant difference in the burnout tendency scores of secondary school teachers based on location.

Method

Research Design

The research design for this study is a correlational survey. A correlational survey is used whenever a researcher is interested in finding out whether there is a relationship between two or more variables, and the data from such variables are in ratio or interval scale. A correlational survey design can be defined as a design that seeks to establish a relationship between two or more variables as well as indicates the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables (Nworgu, 2015). A correlational survey design is deemed appropriate for this study because it seeks to establish a relationship between two variables, namely, the occupational stress and burnout tendencies of secondary school teachers.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised all the 5,634 secondary school teachers in Anambra State, comprising 1,113 male and 4,521 female teachers. (Anambra State Post Primary School Commission, Awka, 2016). These comprise of all the secondary school teachers, in 256 public secondary schools in the State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for the study consists of 2000 teachers. A multi-stage sampling method was adopted for the study. Firstly, simple random sampling technique was used to select five education zones from the existing six education zones in the State. Secondly, simple random sampling technique was used to select schools from each of the five educational zones already selected (Aguata, Awka, Ogidi, Onitsha and Otuocha). Then proportionate stratified random sampling technique was further employed to select 35.5% teachers (males and females) from each of the already selected schools.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instruments that were used for this study include Occupational Stress Inventory for Teachers (OSIT) and Teachers Burnout Inventory (TBI). Occupational stress of secondary school teachers was assessed using a specially developed Occupational Stress Inventory for Teachers (OSIT). The instrument was adapted from Stress Inventory for Teachers originally developed by Sheeja (1999). It was modified by the researchers to suit the purpose of this study. It has 28 items and a 4 point rating scale. For each statement a score of 4, 3, 2 and 1 were given for responses Always, Sometimes, Rarely and Never respectively.

Also, the burnout tendency of secondary school teachers was assessed using the Teachers Burnout Inventory (TBI) developed from Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI). The MBI is a well-known standardised inventory designed to assess three aspects of burnout syndrome: emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and lack of personal accomplishment. It has 24 items and is on a 4 point rating scale ranging from 4 to 1, for responses on strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree respectively.

Validation of the Instrument

The questionnaire was face and content validated by three experts in the Department of Guidance and Counselling and two experts in measurement and evaluation, all from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The topic, the scope and purpose of the study, research Questions, and hypotheses were presented to the experts as guides. These experts ascertained the relevance of items to the research work. The experts made some helpful suggestions and recommended that certain corrections be done which the researchers have duly carried out before the researchers came out with the final instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was established using internal consistency estimate. One hundred secondary school teachers in Delta State were used in a pilot test to establish the reliability of the instrument. The two questionnaires were distributed to the 100 teachers in their schools. These schools in Delta State have been chosen because Delta State shares similar characteristics with Anambra State, the area of study. After the teachers had responded to the instruments, the completed copies were collected and analysed using Cronbach alpha method. Coefficient alpha of 0.877 and 0.934 were obtained for Occupational Stress Inventory for Teachers

(OSIT) and Teachers Burnout Inventory (TBI) respectively. The results indicated a positive and high reliability. Hence the instruments were considered reliable and acceptable for the study.

Method of Data Collection

The researchers made use of extra six well trained research assistants who were Mastersdegree students in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The researchers and the research assistants went round the secondary schools to distribute 2,000 copies of the questionnaires. The respondents were given some minutes or hours to respond to the items. The researchers and the research assistants retrieved the filled copies of the questionnaires for subsequent collation and scoring by the researchers.

Method of Data Analysis

The data relating to research questions one and two were analysed using aggregate scores, percentages. The scores obtained for each of the statements were added together to get the component score as well as the total score for occupational stress and burnout tendency. The total score of stress will vary from 28 - 112 and the burnout scores for the respondents ranged from 24 to 96. Then, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient for research questions 3 to 5. The decision for the Occupational Stress Inventory for teachers; the aggregate scores were grouped into range of three intervals of Low, Moderate and High occupational stress. Ranges of score from 28 - 69.72 were considered as low, range of scores from 70 - 97.72 were considered as Moderate while the range of scores, 98 - 112 were considered as high occupational stress. For the Teachers Burnout Inventory; aggregate scores were also grouped into range of three intervals of Low, Moderate and High burnout tendency. Ranges of score from 24 - 59.76 were recorded as low, range of scores from 60 - 83.76 were recorded as Moderate while the range of scores, 84 - 96 were recorded as high burnout tendency.

Also, data relating to the hypotheses 1-3 were tested using a t-test of correlation coefficient. Hypotheses 4 and 5 were tested using a Z-test; while hypotheses 6 and 7 were tested with Analysis of variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the secondary school teachers occupational stress scores in Anambra state?

Range of Scores	N	%	Remarks
28 to 69.72	985	49.70	Low occupational stress
70 to 97.72	875	44.60	Moderate occupational stress
98 to 112	123	5.70	High occupational stress

Table 1 reveals that 985(49.70%) out of 1983 teachers experience low occupational stress by scoring between 28 and 69.72, while 875(44.60%) of the teachers who scored between 70 and 97.72 experience moderate occupational stress. Also, 123(5.70%) teachers who scored between 98 and 112 experience high occupational stress.

Research question 2

What are the burnout tendency scores of secondary school teachers in Anambra state?

Range of Scores	N	%	Remarks
24 to 59.76	1003	50.60	Low burnout tendency
60 to 83.76	911	45.90	Moderate burnout tendency
84 to 96	69	3.50	High burnout tendency

Table 2 shows that with score ranging from 24 to 59.76, 1003(50.60%) out of 1983 teachers have low burnout tendency, while 911(45.90%) of them who scored between 60 and 83.76 have moderate burnout tendency. Also with scores ranging from 84 to 96, 69(5.50%) of the teachers have high burnout tendency.

Research Question 3

What is the relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of secondary school teachers in Anambra state?

Table 3. Pearson r on the occupational stress and burnout tendency of teachers

N	r	Remark
1983	-0.06	Very low or no relationship

Table 3 reveals that there is very low or no negative relationship of 0.06 existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of secondary school teachers in Anambra state.

Research Question 4

What is the relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of male secondary school teachers in Anambra state?

Table 4. Pearson r on the occupational stress and burnout tendency of male teachers

N	r	Remark
804	0.32	low or negative relationship

Table 4 indicates that there is low negative relationship of -0.32 existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of male secondary school teachers in Anambra state.

Research Question 5

What is the relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of female secondary school teachers in Anambra state?

Table 5. Pearson r on the occupational stress and burnout tendency of female teachers

N	r	Remark
1179	0.19	Very low positive relationship

Table 5 reveals that there is very low positive relationship of 0.19 existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of female secondary school teachers in Anambra state.

Testing the Null Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis 1

The relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of secondary school teachers in Anambra state is not significant.

Table 6:t-test of correlation on the teachers' occupational stress and burnout tendency

N	r	df	Cal.t	Crit.t	P≥0.05
1983	-0.06	1981	2.68	1.96	S

S = Significant

Table 6 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance and 1981df, the calculated t 2.68 is greater than the critical t 1.96. Therefore the first null hypothesis is rejected. There is significant very low or no negative relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of secondary school teachers in Anambra state.

Null Hypothesis 2

The relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of male secondary school teachers in Anambra state is not significant.

Table 7: t-test of correlation on the occupational stress and burnout tendency of male teachers

N	r	df	Cal.t	Crit.t	P≥0.05
804	-0.32	802	9.57	1.96	S

S - Significant

Table 7 reveals that at 0.05 level of significance and 802df, the calculated t 9.57 is greater than the critical t 1.96. Therefore the second null hypothesis is rejected. The low negative relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of male secondary school teachers in Anambra state is significant.

Null Hypothesis 3

The relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of female secondary school teachers in Anambra state is not significant.

Table 8: t-test of correlation on the occupational stress and burnout tendency of female teachers

N	r	df	Cal.t	Crit.t	P≥0.05
1179	0.19	1177	6.64	1.96	S

S = Significant

Table 8 shows that at 0.05 level of significance and 1177df, the calculated t 6.64 is greater than the critical t 1.96. Therefore the third null hypothesis is rejected. The low positive relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of female secondary school teachers in Anambra state is significant.

Null Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in the occupational stress scores of secondary school teachers based on gender.

Table 9: z-test on the mean scores of male and female teachers on their occupational stress

Source of variation	N	X	sd	df	Cal.z	Crit.z	P≥0.05
Male	804		71.75	18.33			
				1981	1.56	1.96	NS
Female	1179	70.53	15.96				

Table 9, indicates that at-0.05 level of significance and 1981 df the calculated z 1.56 is-less than the critical z 1.96. Therefore, the fourth null hypothesis is accepted. So there is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on their occupational Stress.

Null Hypothesis 5

There is no significant difference in the burnout tendency scores of secondary school teachers based on gender.

Table 10: z-test on the mean scores of male and female teachers on their burnout tendency

Source of variation	N	X	sd	df	Cal.z	Crit.z	P>0.05
Male	804	60.98		12.92			
				1981	1.77	1.96	NS
Female	1179	91.94	11.10				

Table 10, shows that at 0.05 level of significance and 1981df the calculated z 1.77 is less than the critical z 1.96. Therefore, the fifth null hypothesis is accepted. So there is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on their burnout tendency.

Null hypothesis 6

There is no significant difference in the occupational stress scores of secondary school teachers based on location.

Table 11:ANOVA on the mean scores of teachers on occupational stress based on location

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	Cal. F	Crit. F	P≥0.05
Between Groups	8673.324	2	4336.662			
Within Groups	561958.562	1980	283.817	15.28	3.00	S
Total	570631.886	1982				

In table 11 it was observed that at 0.05 level of significant, 2df numerator and 1980df denominator, the calculated F 15.28 is greater than the critical F3.00. The sixth null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean scores of secondary school teachers on their occupational stress based on location.

Null hypothesis 7

There is no significant difference in the burnout tendency scores of secondary school teachers based on location.

Table 12: ANOVA on the mean scores of teachers on burnout tendency based on location

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	Cal. F	Crit. F	P≥0.05
Between Groups	3065.708	2	1532.854			
Within Groups Total	276416.744	1980	139.604	10.98	3.00	S
Total	279482.452	1982				

Table 12 shows that 0.05 level of significant, 2df numerator and 1980df denominator, the calculated F 10.98 is greater than the critical F3.00. The seventh null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean scores of secondary school teachers on their burnout tendency based on location.

Discussion of Findings

The occupational stress of secondary school teachers in Anambra state

Findings of this study revealed that majority of teachers (49.70%) experience low occupational stress, while only few teachers (5.70%) experience high occupational stress. However, many of the teachers (44.60%) experience moderate occupational stress. Findings from this study are equally in line with findings of Lokanadha and Poomima (2012) whose study revealed that majority (74%) of the teachers are experiencing moderate and high levels of occupational stress. The study reveals that stress has become widespread amongst teachers, and that the reviewed studies are providing insight into the extent of the problem and how it could possibly be managed. In both categories, the proportions found were much greater than for the general population. On the difference in the occupational stress scores of secondary school teachers based on gender, the study revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on their occupational stress. This finding agrees with Akomolafe (2011) who reported that there was no significant difference between the occupational stress experienced by male and female secondary school teachers. In contrast however, later findings in Aftab and Khatoon (2012) reported that nearly half of the secondary school teachers experience less stress towards their job and males display more occupational stress towards job than the females.

This finding is however a little surprising to the researchers as it is expected that females, especially married ones experience more stress by far when compared to their male counterpart. The reason for this is that women engage in dual occupations, combining management of home with all the other workloads in school.

On whether there is any significant difference in the occupational stress scores of secondary school female teachers based on location, findings from the study revealed that there is significant difference in the mean scores of secondary school teachers on their occupational stress based on location. This result agrees with the findings of Lokanadha and Poomima (2012), but disagrees with Aftab and Khatoon (2012), reporting that Teacher stress was not directly associated with school location, size and class size.

The burnout tendencies of secondary school teachers

Findings from the study revealed that most of the teachers (50.60%) have low burnout tendency, while only few teachers (3.50%) have high burnout tendency. More so, 45.90% of teachers have moderate burnout tendency. This finding is in agrees with earlier findings of Akomolafe (2011). Finding of the study, thus, further agrees with those of previous studies on burnout Jonas (2001); Maslach, Schaufeli & Leiter, 2005). Findings from the study have indicated that the common symptoms of job burnout for teachers as noted from the study include dissatisfaction, emotional, physical and mental fatigue, feelings of helplessness and hopelessness; and a lack of enthusiasm about work and or life in general.

On whether there is a significant difference in the burnout tendency scores of secondary school teachers based on gender, the result from this study reveals that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on their burnout tendency. This finding is in agreement with results from previous studies. For example, Aftab and Khatoon (2012) reported that gender was not a predictor of burnout in their sample, findings from their study showed that in general gender has no effect on burnout level of the teachers.

Findings from the study equally showed that there is significant difference in the mean scores of secondary school teachers on their burnout tendency based on location. Findings from these studies have shown that there is more to teachers' stress and burnout tendency. According to Dorman (2012), teaching is a very stressful occupation with negative aspects such as unmotivated and difficult students, decreasing resources, larger class sizes, and rigid administration practices, which can sometimes lead to teacher burnout. Teacher burnout has long been understood to have significant negative effects on teaching efficacy.

The relationship between the occupational stress and burnout

Findings from the study revealed that there is very low or no negative relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of secondary school teachers in Anambra state. This finding agrees with the findings from earlier studies such as the study by Lokanadha and Poomima(2012) whose analysis showed strong support for the hypothesis that there is a positive relationship between the occupational stress and burnout of school teachers. The study by Lokanadha and Poomima (2012) found that many of the educators who experienced stress also suffered from burnout.

Findings from the study further revealed that the low or no negative relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of secondary school teachers in Anambra state is significant. This is in line with results from the study of some past researchers which showed that there were significant correlation among occupational stress, teacher burnout and mental health. More studies like (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004; Hassan, 2014) have also revealed that occupational stress that consists of job demands and a lack of resources may lead to burnout. Findings from the research study further revealed that the low negative relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of male secondary school teachers in Anambra state is significant. It also revealed that the low positive relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of female secondary school teachers in Anambra state is significant. This means that increase in stress does not lead to increase in burnout tendency and vice versa among male teachers in Anambra state.

Conclusion

There is a relationship existing between occupational stress and burnout tendency of secondary school teachers in Anambra state. Also, while there is low negative relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of male secondary school teachers, there is very

low positive relationship existing between the occupational stress and burnout tendency of female secondary school teachers in Anambra state.

Implications of the Study

The findings of this study have a number of implications for counselling, school administration and management. The findings from the study revealed that teachers experience low or moderate occupational stress. There is a relationship between occupational stress and burnout. Thus, there is need to put what leads to occupational stress of teachers on check in order to ensure that it does not become high. Also, policy makers in education, national bodies, school administrators, teachers and counsellors need to work towards managing the stressors that cause prolonged stress among teachers. Putting measures to prevent or minimise the chances of teachers' occupational stress becoming higher.

Findings also indicated that secondary school teachers are experiencing low burnout tendency. This may be due to a number of reasons. However, Guidance counsellors have a serious role to play here. Various stress reduction measures and interventions could be put in place to help teachers already exposed to stress. There is need to find ways of addressing such to reduce the tendency to burnout among teachers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and implications of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is need to introduce stress management programmes, say for example emotional intelligence training which helps the teachers to be self-aware of the abilities and skills required for the range of roles, responsibilities and demands of their work, manage emotional reactions to specific situations and people.
2. Staff support for school teachers through supervision should be introduced in schools. This will help provide support, change perceptions, manage emotions and cope with stressful situations and in so doing will help eliminate stress, improved teachers' work performance and relationship with others.
3. with regard to the burnout tendency, the schools should see the need to develop mechanisms and appropriate measures to detect the stressors causing strain among the school teachers. They can Organize meetings; seminars, workshops, professional development courses, and other activities to help teachers to weed out stress and eliminate chances of burnout tendency.

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